

FIBER CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY MIXTURES BASED ON LOCAL MATERIALS

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Abstract: For successful application of basalt fiber concrete in monolithic construction, there must be an available efficient technology for frequently used compositions of such concrete. This article presents the results of research and recommendations on efficient technology of basalt fiber concrete.

The conducted studies allowed to establish that the introduction of basalt fiber into the composition of heavy concrete according to the proposed technology helps to increase the compressive strength limit by 15% compared to the same indicator of concrete without microreinforcement. At the same time, it is possible to save cement consumption by up to 10% or more.

Keywords: basalt fiber concrete, basalt, fiber, testing, strength, technology, composition.

Introduction

From the results of numerous experimental and theoretical studies [1,2,3] it is known that the process of concrete destruction under load begins with cracks at the contacts between the cement stone and large aggregates. These cracks mainly develop along the compression forces, but may have some deviation due to transverse expansion deformations. The destruction of the compressed sample occurs due to the rupture of concrete in the transverse direction, first, microcracks of separation appear, which subsequently, with increasing load, merge and form visible cracks, leading to the destruction of the concrete sample. For high-quality splitting of basalt fiber bundles into individual units and their uniform distribution by volume during mixing of concrete components, a more accessible technology is needed, which can be based on changing the order of preparation of such concrete mixtures.

An important point in the preparation of concrete mix is the correct assignment of the ratio of components of the concrete mix, since the quality and strength of the concrete largely depend on this.

It is recommended to mix the components of fiber concrete (binding fillers and dispersed reinforcement) usually in forced-action concrete mixers in two stages - at the first stage, the components of concrete in dry form are mixed for at least 3 minutes, at the second stage, after adding water, they are also mixed for at least 3 minutes. According to the authors [4], this mode allows the bundles of basalt fibers to split into individual units. The use of basalt fibers according to this technology for preparing concrete mix at its optimal content, according to the author, allows to increase the tensile strength of concrete in bending up to 70% or more compared to similar indicators of concrete without dispersed reinforcement.

Materials and test methods

Ahangarancement "was used to conduct experimental studies, which meets the requirements of GOST 10178-85 "Portland cement and slag Portland cement. Technical conditions".

the manufacturer's data, the normal density of cement paste is 27%, the specific surface is 3500 cm²/g. The activity of cement by strength on the day of testing is 38.5 MPa .

from the Kuylyuk quarry, which meets the requirements of GOST 10260 [5], was used as a large aggregate for the preparation of the concrete mixture.

from the Kuylyuk quarry, which meets the requirements of GOST 8736 [6], was used as fine aggregate.

Basalt fiber is a section of complex basalt fiber of a given length in the form of loose monofilaments. Basalt is produced OOO MEGA INVEST INDUSTRIAL ». Basalt fiber has the following technical characteristics: color – bronze; density – 2.8 g/cm³; diameter of individual fiber – 13-20 μm; fiber length: 5, 10, 15 and 20 mm; operating temperature from -260 to +700°C; melting point – 1450°C; tensile strength – 45-55 Gs / tex; resistant to acids and alkalis.

Basalt fiber concrete technology

The properties of basalt fiber provide high performance of concrete with its use, which is associated with the modification of the concrete matrix and giving it special properties for resistance to various aggressive influences.

When preparing a fiber concrete mixture, the fiber is introduced at the stage of production of the concrete mixture, which acts as a reinforcing component, compatibility with all chemical additives and rapid distribution of fibers throughout the volume of the mixture without clumping occurs [4,8]. How this technology modifies bundles of basalt fibers into individual fibers is not entirely clear. The fact is that when adding basalt fiber (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Basalt fibers used in the experiments

in the almost prepared concrete mixture there are no conditions for its splitting into separate units, since the fibers in their original form will begin to stick to the cement-sand mortar and form lumps. In this regard, mechanical or other external influences are necessary to split the bundles of basalt fibers. In this case, the bundles of basalt fibers should split by at least 70-80%, without damaging the properties of the fiber. It can be expected that the surface and shape of the fibers will not be greatly deformed by mechanical influences, which will contribute to their uniform dispersion and adhesion to the cement mortar. After analyzing the existing

technologies for preparing basalt fiber concrete mixture, we can draw some conclusions: it is recommended to mix basalt fiber only when preparing concrete mixture in forced-action mixers, there is no way to control the splitting and dispersion of fiber bundles, which in their original state will be together with all the components of concrete, as its separate component. As follows from the above analysis, first of all, in all likelihood, it is necessary to slightly change the composition of basalt fiber concrete itself by adjusting the proportion of large aggregate in the aggregate mixture, reducing its consumption, and accordingly increasing the proportion of sand. The composition is calculated as for ordinary heavy concrete with some adjustment by introducing a decreasing coefficient of 0.85 for the consumption of large aggregate, its volume is replenished by increasing the consumption by introducing an increasing coefficient of 1.2 on the calculated values of these indicators. The structure of concrete, unlike the traditional one, allows the most complete use of the volume of intergranular voids of crushed stone for uniform distribution of basalt fibers throughout its volume. At the same time, the efficiency of basalt fiber concrete compositions will be determined by the appointment of the optimal grain

composition of fillers, providing minimal voids due to the dense arrangement of fibers in the composition of the cement-sand mortar of concrete.

Research results

When selecting the concrete composition, we relied on two main assumptions, based on the structural features of heavy concrete based on Portland cement. The first is to ensure maximum strength of the cement-sand concrete mortar with the minimum possible consumption of large aggregate, based on the fact that after the introduction of basalt fiber, the strength of the mortar will increase sharply and good adhesion (bondage) with large aggregate and the required reinforcement effect will be achieved without compromising the technology of basalt fiber concrete.

The second condition is to ensure the required mobility of the basalt fiber concrete mixture at various frequently used binder consumption rates (350-550 kg/m³) and water-cement ratio with the optimal aggregate consumption, which is determined by both the technology and the expected concrete strength. In addition, the recommended technology for preparing the basalt fiber concrete mixture should be based on the use of existing mixing equipment for mixing the five-component concrete composition. A gravity mixer was used for this purpose.

Mixing of concrete mixture in such mixers is carried out due to the action of gravity on it. During rotation, the blades pick up, lift and throw down streams of mixture.

The basalt fiber concrete mixture was prepared in a laboratory mixer of a similar type. In this case, unlike other technologies of such concrete, two variants of the sequence of loading the concrete components were considered.

After testing the existing and proposed technology for preparing basalt fiber concrete mixture, we came to the conclusion that the best method was the preliminary separate displacement of 50% of the amount of crushed stone with fiber, introduced in 3-4 portions, as well as another method - initially 50% of crushed stone plus 50% of sand is loaded and basalt fiber is introduced.

The first method is to load the required amount of basalt fiber into the mixer drum after loading 50% of the amount of crushed stone and mix it with it for 3-5 minutes. Then pour the rest of the crushed stone and sand into the mixer. With the unit turned on, pour in water and add cement. Continue mixing the batch until the desired consistency is achieved (about 5-7 minutes).

The second method is to load the required amount of basalt fiber into the mixer drum after loading crushed stone and sand in an amount of 50% each and mix them together for at least 5 minutes. Then add the remaining parts of crushed stone and sand into the mixer. With the unit turned on, pour in water and add cement. Continue mixing until the desired consistency is achieved (about 5-7 minutes). In this case, a two-stage modification of basalt fibers occurs. Condition and types of basalt fiber concrete mixtures prepared using the technology described above are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. View of basalt fiber concrete mixture after unloading from the mixer. a - according to the first method; b - the same, according to the second method.

From these mixtures, concrete cubes with 10 cm rib dimensions were made, which after stripping were tested for compression in a MIG-1000 hydraulic press [7].

The composition of the concrete was determined as follows:

cement – 425 kg/m³; crushed granite fr.5-20 mm – 950 kg/m³; quartz sand – 815 kg/m³; water – 210 l/m³; basalt fiber 1% of the cement weight. No negative phenomena were observed during the production of cube samples. The test results are presented in the table.

Method of preparation - leniya	Return of concrete on the day of testing, days .	Strength of concrete without additives, MPa	Strength of basalt fiber concrete, MPa	Strength increase, %
According to option 1	7	22.6	25.8	14
	14	26.1	30.2	15.8
	28	30.2	34.8	15.2
According to option II	7	22.6	26.4	16.8
	14	26.1	31.0	18.7
	28	30.2	34.2	13.2

As follows from the data in the table, in all comparable test conditions, there is an increase in the strength of basalt fiber concrete (on average by 15%) compared to the strength of concrete of similar compositions without basalt fibers. The increase in strength is directly related to the introduction of basalt fibers into the concrete composition, leading to an improvement in its structure formation during the process of cement hydration and concrete hardening.

Technological recommendations have been developed that allow for further improvement of other concrete compositions and development of basalt fiber concrete production based on local materials. In order to confirm the results of laboratory studies, work is currently underway to test them in production conditions.

Conclusions

- one of the ways to solve problems of improving the strength and durability characteristics of concrete is to introduce basalt fibers into their composition. At present, such concretes on cement binders have limited areas of application in load-bearing structures, despite the technical advantages;

- compositions and technology for producing basalt fiber concrete mixtures have been developed, which make it possible to improve the performance of such concretes due to a more uniform distribution of fibers throughout the volume of concrete;
- selection of basalt fiber concrete compositions with frequently used cement consumption rates should be based on selection of concrete compositions calculated by the calculation and experimental method based on absolute volumes with a reduction in the consumption of coarse aggregate and adjustment of sand consumption. At the same time, its consumption rate should not exceed the consumption rate of coarse aggregate;
- an effective technology of basalt fiber concrete should be based on the splitting of basalt fibers at the initial stage of preparation of the mixture by mixing with half of the coarse aggregate (first method) or with half of the coarse aggregate and half of the sand combined (second method). With this technology it will be possible to achieve maximum splitting of basalt fibers and their uniform distribution;
- the compressive strength of basalt fiber concrete samples manufactured using the recommended technology, with a basalt fiber content of 1%, results in an increase in the same characteristic by 15% compared to a composition without additives;
- the technical and technological advantages inherent in basalt fiber concrete give grounds to conclude that this study should be continued with the aim of using basalt fiber for reinforcing load-bearing concrete and reinforced concrete structures.

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